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 Sample Name: Proszki

C_Si 8_2

eZAF Quant Result - Analysis Uncertainty: 11.46 %

Element	Weight %	MDL	Atomic %	Error %
C K	88.0	0.01	93.7	6.2
O K	2.4	0.01	1.9	8.6
Si K	9.6	0.02	4.4	5.7

/Lukasiewicz 25.02.25/Proszki/C_Si 8_2/Full Area 1/

kV: 5 Mag: 500 Takeoff: 35.5 Live Time(s): 299.5 Amp Time(μs): 0.96 Resolution:(eV) 131.6

Det: Element-C2B